

On the refractive index and curvature relation

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We formulate a relation of the refractive index and curvature in local space-time geometry using the Ricci curvature tensor and its extension to global space-time geometry as the relation of the refractive index and an Abelian curvature form.

Keywords: *geometrical optics, Abelian gauge theory, refractive index, Ricci curvature tensor, curvature form.*

I. INTRODUCTION

It is a common understanding that the refractive index has nothing to do with global space-time geometry and in turn with topology. The refractive index is a property of the medium (specifically its permittivity and permeability) that describes the local response of the medium to electromagnetic waves (how light bends or slows down in the medium). It is a local, material-dependent quantity and has no direct connection to topological invariants. The refractive index describes the local optical properties of a material rather than global topological properties. Topological invariants are more closely related to the structure and behavior of space-time on a global scale, not to material-specific properties like refractive index. The refractive index being 1 in a vacuum is just a physical constant that represents the speed of light in that medium and does not have the same topological significance as, say, a winding number.

We formulate a relation of the refractive index and curvature in local space-time geometry using the Ricci curvature tensor. We extend this local to global space-time geometry as the relation of the refractive index and an Abelian curvature form. To the best of our knowledge^{1,3}, the formulation of the refractive index and curvature relation in local space-time geometry using the Ricci curvature tensor and its extension to global space-time geometry (as the relation of the refractive index and an Abelian curvature form) has not been done.

If we consider the refractive index being 1 in a vacuum space-time as an integer number, then could this integer number of the refractive index be interpreted as a topological invariant? How about the form of the refractive index and curvature relation formulated in global space-time geometry?

II. THE REFRACTIVE INDEX AND CURVATURE

In the geometrical optics, the refractive index-curvature relation derived from the Fermat's principle describes ray propagation in a steady (time-independent) state¹. The refractive index and curvature² relation can

be written as^{1,3-5}

$$\frac{1}{R} = \hat{N} \cdot \vec{\nabla} \ln n(r) \quad (1)$$

where R is a radius of curvature¹, \hat{N} is an unit vector along the principal normal or has the same direction with $\vec{\nabla} \ln n(r)$. Here, $\vec{\nabla} \ln n(r)$ means the gradient of a function $\ln n$ at a point r and $n(r)$ is a space-dependent refractive index, a scalar function of the coordinates only (a smooth continuous function of the position⁶). Eq.(24) is a type of the first order non-linear partial differential equation. The nonlinearity is due to $\vec{\nabla} \ln n(r)$. Physically, eq.(24) tells us that the rays are therefore bent in the direction of increasing refractive index¹.

We see eq.(24) is a dot product of two vectors, so the result gives a scalar quantity

$$\hat{N} \cdot \vec{\nabla} \ln n(r) = \sum_{i=1}^d N_i \nabla_i \ln n(r) \quad (2)$$

where d is a number of dimension of space.

By substituting eq.(2) into eq.(24), we obtain

$$\frac{1}{R} = \sum_{i=1}^d N_i \nabla_i \ln n(r) \quad (3)$$

In the following, we will see the formulation of eq.(3) in the case of three-dimensional space.

III. THE REFRACTIVE INDEX AND RICCI CURVATURE

In the case of three dimensional space⁷, we can write eq.(3) as

$$R_{\mu\nu} = g_{\mu\nu} N_{(\mu} \partial_{\nu)} \ln n \quad (4)$$

where $R_{\mu\nu}$ is the second rank tensor of Ricci curvature, $g_{\mu\nu}$ is the metric tensor, $\mu, \nu = 1, 2, 3$, are space-time coordinates. We write $N_{(\mu} \partial_{\nu)}$ in eq.(25) to accommodate the symmetry property of the second rank tensor of Ricci curvature, $R_{\mu\nu} \equiv R_{\nu\mu}$, where $N_{(\mu} \partial_{\nu)} = \frac{1}{2}(N_{\mu} \partial_{\nu} + N_{\nu} \partial_{\mu})$.

The zeroth rank tensor (a scalar, a real number) of the refractive index (24), (25), describes an isotropic linear optics¹¹. But, the refractive index can be not simply a scalar¹². The refractive index can also be a second rank tensor which describes the electric field component along one axis may be affected by the electric field component along another axis¹². The second rank tensor of the refractive index describes an anisotropic linear optics¹¹.

IV. THE GEOMETRICAL OPTICS AS AN U(1) LOCAL GAUGE THEORY

The geometrical optics can be derived from the Maxwell's theory, an Abelian $U(1)$ local gauge theory¹³. Roughly speaking, the Maxwell's theory is a special case of a non-Abelian Yang-Mills gauge theory. That is why, in this article, we treat the geometrical optics as an Abelian $U(1)$ local gauge theory⁵.

V. CURVATURE IN A FIBRE BUNDLE

We will formulate a curvature in a fibre bundle. Why do we need to formulate a curvature in a fibre bundle instead of the Riemann-Christoffel curvature tensor? Riemann curvature tensor is related to local, instead global geometry. Fibre bundle could accomodate a global geometry. A curvature form in a fibre bundle can be an Abelian or a non-Abelian (a non-linear). It differs with the Riemann-Christoffel curvature tensor which has the non-linear form only¹⁵.

The curvature form, $\Omega_{\alpha\mu}$, in a fibre bundle can be written as^{16,17}

$$\Omega_{\alpha\mu} = \sum R_{\alpha\mu\beta\nu} du^\beta \wedge du^\nu \quad (5)$$

where $R_{\alpha\mu\beta\nu}$ is the fourth rank tensor of Riemann-Christoffel curvature (which has the algebraic properties as symmetry, anti-symmetry and cyclicity¹⁰), u^β , u^ν are local coordinates and \wedge is a notation of the exterior (wedge) product (it satisfies the distributive, anti-commutative¹⁸, wedge and associative laws)^{16,17}. $\Omega_{\alpha\mu}$ is an anti-symmetric matrix of two-forms^{20,21}. We consider an anti-symmetric property of the curvature form is related to the anti-commutative property of the exterior product and two-forms is related to two-dimensions of $du^\beta \wedge du^\nu$.

Let us introduce a general form of the curvature matrix, Ω , which is a matrix of exterior two-forms^{16,22} below

$$\Omega = d\omega - \omega \wedge \omega \quad (6)$$

where ω is the connection matrix, one-form^{23,24}, $d\omega$ and $\omega \wedge \omega$ are two-forms. We see that eq.(28) is a non-linear equation due to the second term of the right hand side of eq.(28).

VI. A GAUGE THEORY AND A FIBRE BUNDLE

Is there a relationship between a fibre bundle and a gauge theory? Originally, a fibre bundle and a gauge theory are developed independently. Until it was realized that a curvature (in a fibre bundle) and the field strength (in Yang-Mills gauge theory) are identical¹⁴.

As a consequence of the geometrical optics treatment as an Abelian $U(1)$ local gauge theory, we need to formulate a curvature in a fibre bundle as what we call an Abelian (a linear) curvature form.

A gauge potential, \mathcal{A} , can be regarded as a local expression for a connection in a principal bundle²³

$$\mathcal{A} = \sigma^* \omega \quad (7)$$

where σ is a local section defined on a chart U of manifold, base space, M . The local form of the curvature is defined by²³

$$\mathcal{F} \equiv \sigma^* \Omega \quad (8)$$

where \mathcal{F} is identified with the field strength. In a general case, from Cartan's structure equation, we find²³

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{F} &= \sigma^*(d_p \omega + \omega \wedge \omega) = d\sigma^* \omega + \sigma^* \omega \wedge \sigma^* \omega \\ &= d\mathcal{A} + \mathcal{A} \wedge \mathcal{A} \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

where d is the exterior derivative on M . We see from eqs.(30), (31) that

$$\Omega = d_p \omega + \omega \wedge \omega \quad (10)$$

and

$$\sigma^* d_p \omega = d\sigma^* \omega \quad (11)$$

We consider eq.(33) as an identity for the connection matrix, one-form, where a local section, σ , is a map^{39,41}.

In a special case, for an Abelian $U(1)$ local gauge theory, using eq.(29) and the fact that the exterior derivative obeys the Leibniz rule²⁵, \mathcal{F} can be expressed in terms of the gauge potential \mathcal{A} ²³ as below

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{F} &= d\mathcal{A} \\ \sigma^* d_p \omega &= d(\sigma^* \omega) = d\sigma^* \omega + \sigma^* d\omega \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

Eq.(34) implies

$$\Omega = d_p \omega \quad (13)$$

where d_p means the covariant derivative of a vector valued one-form, ω , on a principal bundle, $P(M, G)$, G is structure group²³. So, $d_p \omega$ is two-forms. We see that eq.(35) is an Abelian, a linear equation.

Let us consider $d\mathcal{A}$ in eqs.(31), (34). $d\mathcal{A}$ in such both equations should be the same or in other words as a consequence of eq.(33), $d\omega$ in eq.(34) should be zero

$$d\omega = 0 \quad (14)$$

It means that the connection matrix, one-form, ω , is closed if $d\omega = 0$ ^{23,26,27}.

Can we see something interesting in eqs.(33), (36)? $d\omega = 0$ (36) implies that ω is closed (on the boundary of the region of a solution surface⁴⁰). It can be shown using the Stokes theorem^{17,39,40} written below

$$\int_M d\omega = \oint_{\partial M} \omega \quad (15)$$

We can say that the identity for the connection matrix, one-form (33), has a consequence that $d\omega = 0$ (36). We can write the exterior derivative of the connection matrix on manifold equal to zero as $d\omega|_M = 0$, i.e. $d\omega$ in a suitable region U of a solution surface M ⁴⁰. So, we can write the left and the right hand sides of the Stokes theorem eq.(37) respectively as $\int_U d\omega|_M = 0$ and $\oint_{\partial U} \omega|_M = 0$ ⁴⁰. This $\oint_{\partial U} \omega|_M = 0$ is a kind of integral conservation law⁴⁰. Does it mean ω can be related to a conserved quantity in physics? What kind of such conserved quantity?

Is there a relationship between the curvature matrix, Ω (28), and the curvature form, $\Omega_{\alpha\mu}$ (26)? Yes (there is)²⁸. If $\Omega_{\alpha\mu}$ and $\omega_{\alpha\mu}$ denote the components of curvature and connection matrices, Ω and ω , respectively then we can write¹⁶

$$\Omega = (\Omega_{\alpha\mu}), \quad \omega = (\omega_{\alpha\mu}) \quad (16)$$

So, the curvature matrices in eqs.(32), (35) can be written using the curvature form¹⁷ respectively as below

$$\Omega_{\alpha\mu} = d_p \omega_{\alpha\mu} - \omega_{\alpha}^{\tau} \wedge \omega_{\mu\tau} \quad (17)$$

and

$$\Omega_{\alpha\mu} = d_p \omega_{\alpha\mu} \quad (18)$$

We call eq.(40) as an Abelian (a linear) curvature form equation.

VII. THE REFRACTIVE INDEX AND AN ABELIAN CURVATURE FORM

If we reformulate eq.(26) using eq.(25) and the Ricci-Riemann relation in a 2-dimensional space, $R_{\alpha\mu\beta\nu} = (g_{\alpha\beta} g_{\mu\nu} - g_{\alpha\nu} g_{\mu\beta}) \frac{R_{\mu\nu}}{g_{\mu\nu}}$, then we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} & \sum (g_{\alpha\beta} g_{\mu\nu} - g_{\alpha\nu} g_{\mu\beta}) N_{(\mu} \partial_{\nu)} \ln n du^{\beta} \wedge du^{\nu} \\ & = \Omega_{\alpha\mu} \end{aligned} \quad (19)$$

Eq.(27) shows the relationship between the scalar refractive index and the curvature form in a 2-dimensional space. It means that the scalar refractive index "lives" in a 2-dimensional space.

Can we construct an Abelian, a linear equation as a special case of the non-Abelian, non-linear curvature matrix equation (28)?

As we mentioned that we treat the geometrical optics as an Abelian $U(1)$ local gauge theory, so we choose the curvature form (40) to describe the geometrical optics. By substituting eq.(27) into eq.(40), we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} & \sum (g_{\alpha\beta} g_{\mu\nu} - g_{\alpha\nu} g_{\mu\beta}) N_{(\mu} \partial_{\nu)} \ln n du^{\beta} \wedge du^{\nu} \\ & = d_p \omega_{\alpha\mu} \end{aligned} \quad (20)$$

We call eq.(41) as an Abelian curvature form-scalar refractive index relation.

VIII. THE REFRACTIVE INDEX AND THE PFAFFIAN

Let us define the pfaffian²⁹ of the curvature matrix, Ω , as below^{16,30}

$$\text{pf } \Omega \equiv \sum \varepsilon_{\alpha_1 \mu_1 \dots \alpha_{2q} \mu_{2q}} \Omega_{\alpha_1 \mu_1} \wedge \dots \wedge \Omega_{\alpha_{2q} \mu_{2q}} \quad (21)$$

where the curvature matrix, Ω , is any even-size complex $2q \times 2q$ anti-symmetric matrix (if Ω is an odd-size complex anti-symmetric matrix then the corresponding pfaffian is defined to be zero), $\varepsilon_{\alpha_1 \mu_1 \dots \alpha_{2q} \mu_{2q}}$ is the $2q$ -th rank Levi-Civita tensor which has value +1 or -1 according as its indices form an even or odd permutation of $1, \dots, 2q$, and its otherwise zero, and the sum is extended over all indices from 1 to $2q$, q is a natural number. Here, $\alpha_1 < \mu_1, \dots, \alpha_{2q} < \mu_{2q}$ and $\alpha_1 < \alpha_2 < \dots < \alpha_{2q}$ ^{16,30}. Shortly, the pfaffian of Ω (42) can be rewritten as

$$\text{pf } \Omega = \sum \varepsilon_{\alpha\mu} \Omega_{\alpha\mu} \quad (22)$$

By substituting eqs.(40), (41) into eq.(43) we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} & \sum \varepsilon_{\alpha\mu} \sum (g_{\alpha\beta} g_{\mu\nu} - g_{\alpha\nu} g_{\mu\beta}) N_{(\mu} \partial_{\nu)} \ln n du^{\beta} \wedge du^{\nu} \\ & = \text{pf } \Omega \end{aligned} \quad (23)$$

IX. DISCUSSIONS AND CONCLUSIONS

Physics is often understood as a local phenomenon, focusing on local instead of global space-time geometries. This local perspective may overlook crucial aspects of our understanding of the full behavior of physical systems. However, global space-time geometry offers insights that local geometry might miss. Interestingly, global space-time geometry is fundamentally linked to topology. Topology, in turn, can often be characterized by integer-valued topological invariants, which capture global properties of space-time.

The pfaffian of the curvature matrix (43) is defined to be zero or non-zero if the curvature matrix is an odd-size or an even-size complex anti-symmetric matrix respectively. In turn, the zero or non-zero curvature form (26) has a consequence that the Riemann-Christoffel curvature tensor is vanish or not vanish respectively. The vanishing Riemann-Christoffel curvature tensor means vacuum space. In other words, the Riemann-Christoffel curvature tensor must vanish in vacuum space³⁸. So, does it mean that the zero or non-zero curvature form is related to vacuum or non-vacuum space (in turn a vanishing or a non-vanishing field strength?)

We see from eq.(36) that the connection matrix, one-form, ω , is closed. What is the meaning of a closed one-form physically? Could we interpret $d\omega = 0$ related to

a conserved quantity (conservation law) in physics, especially in the geometrical optics? What is such conserved quantity in the geometrical optics?

We formulate the Gauss-Bonnet-Chern theorem in geometrical optics using Pfaffian. We interpret that the scalar refractive index could take a role as a topological invariant.

In the geometrical optics, the refractive index-curvature relation derived from the Fermat's principle describes ray propagation in a steady (time-independent) state¹. The refractive index-curvature² relation can be written as^{1,3-5}

$$\frac{1}{R} = \hat{N} \cdot \vec{\nabla} \ln n(r) \quad (24)$$

where R is a radius of curvature¹, \hat{N} is an unit vector along the principal normal or has the same direction with $\vec{\nabla} \ln n(r)$, $\vec{\nabla} \ln n(r)$ means the gradient of a function $\ln n$ at a point r and $n(r)$ is a space-dependent refractive index, a scalar function of the coordinates only (a smooth continuous function of the position⁶). We see eq.(24) is a dot product of two vectors, so the result gives a scalar quantity, $\hat{N} \cdot \vec{\nabla} \ln n(r) = \sum_{i=1}^{dim} N_i \nabla_i \ln n(r)$, dim is a number of dimension of space. Eq.(24) is a type of the first order non-linear partial differential equation. The nonlinearity is due to $\vec{\nabla} \ln n(r)$. Physically, eq.(24) tells us that the rays are therefore bent in the direction of increasing refractive index¹.

X. THE RICCI CURVATURE-REFRACTIVE INDEX RELATION

In a 2-dimensional space⁷, we write eq.(24) as

$$R_{\mu\nu} = g_{\mu\nu} N_{(\mu} \partial_{\nu)} \ln n \quad (25)$$

where $R_{\mu\nu}$ is the second rank tensor of Ricci curvature^{8,9}, $R_{\mu\nu} = g_{\mu\nu} \frac{R_{1212}}{g}$ ¹⁰, a function of the metric tensor $g_{\mu\nu}$, $g = |(\det g_{\mu\nu})|$ is a scalar density¹⁰, a real number, and μ, ν run from 1 to 2. We write $N_{(\mu} \partial_{\nu)}$ in eq.(25) to accomodate the symmetry property of the second rank tensor of Ricci curvature, $R_{\mu\nu} \equiv R_{\nu\mu}$, where $N_{(\mu} \partial_{\nu)} = \frac{1}{2}(N_{\mu} \partial_{\nu} + N_{\nu} \partial_{\mu})$.

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The geometrical optics can be derived from the Maxwell's theory, an Abelian $U(1)$ local gauge theory¹³. That is why, in this article we treat the geometrical optics as an Abelian $U(1)$ local gauge theory⁵. We will formulate a curvature in a fibre bundle. Is there a relationship between a fibre bundle and a gauge theory? Originally, a

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XI. THE CURVATURE FORM-REFRACTIVE INDEX RELATION

The curvature form, $\Omega_{\alpha\mu}$, in a fibre bundle can be written as^{16,17}

$$\Omega_{\alpha\mu} = \sum R_{\alpha\mu\beta\nu} du^{\beta} \wedge du^{\nu} \quad (26)$$

where $R_{\alpha\mu\beta\nu}$ is the fourth rank tensor of Riemann-Christoffel curvature (which has the algebraic properties as symmetry, anti-symmetry and cyclicity¹⁰), u^{β} , u^{ν} are local coordinates and \wedge is a notation of the exterior (wedge) product (it satisfies the distributive, anti-commutative¹⁸, wedge and associative laws)^{16,17}. $\Omega_{\alpha\mu}$ is an anti-symmetric matrix of two-forms^{20,21}. Why is $\Omega_{\alpha\mu}$ an anti-symmetric matrix of two-forms? We consider an anti-symmetric property of the curvature form is related to the anti-commutative property of the exterior product and two-forms is related to two-dimensions of $du^{\beta} \wedge du^{\nu}$.

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Eq.(27) shows the relationship between the scalar refractive index and the curvature form in a 2-dimensional space. It means that the scalar refractive index "lives" in a 2-dimensional space.

Let us introduce a general form of the curvature matrix, Ω , which is a matrix of exterior two-forms^{16,22} below

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$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{F} &= \sigma^*(d_p \omega + \omega \wedge \omega) = d\sigma^* \omega + \sigma^* \omega \wedge \sigma^* \omega \\ &= d\mathcal{A} + \mathcal{A} \wedge \mathcal{A} \end{aligned} \quad (31)$$

where d is the exterior derivative on M . We see from eqs.(30), (31) that

$$\Omega = d_p \omega + \omega \wedge \omega \quad (32)$$

and

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We consider eq.(33) as an identity for the connection matrix, one-form, where a local section, σ , is a map^{39,41}.

In a special case, for an Abelian $U(1)$ local gauge theory, using eq.(29) and the fact that the exterior derivative obeys the Leibniz rule²⁵, \mathcal{F} can be expressed in terms of the gauge potential \mathcal{A} ²³ as below

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Eq.(34) implies

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where d_p means the covariant derivative of a vector valued one-form, ω , on a principal bundle, $P(M, G)$, G is structure group²³. So, $d_p \omega$ is two-forms. We see that eq.(35) is an Abelian, a linear equation.

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$$\Omega = (\Omega_{\alpha\mu}), \quad \omega = (\omega_{\alpha\mu}) \quad (38)$$

So, the curvature matrices in eqs.(32), (35) can be written using the curvature form¹⁷ respectively as below

$$\Omega_{\alpha\mu} = d_p \omega_{\alpha\mu} - \omega_{\alpha}^{\tau} \wedge \omega_{\mu\tau} \quad (39)$$

and

$$\Omega_{\alpha\mu} = d_p \omega_{\alpha\mu} \quad (40)$$

We call eq.(40) as an Abelian (a linear) curvature form equation.

As we mentioned that we treat the geometrical optics as an Abelian $U(1)$ local gauge theory, so we choose the curvature form (40) to describe the geometrical optics. By substituting eq.(27) into eq.(40), we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} &\sum (g_{\alpha\beta} g_{\mu\nu} - g_{\alpha\nu} g_{\mu\beta}) N_{(\mu} \partial_{\nu)} \ln n du^{\beta} \wedge du^{\nu} \\ &= d_p \omega_{\alpha\mu} \end{aligned} \quad (41)$$

We call eq.(41) as an Abelian curvature form-scalar refractive index relation.

Let us define the pfaffian²⁹ of the curvature matrix, pf Ω , as below^{16,30}

$$\text{pf } \Omega \equiv \sum \epsilon_{\alpha_1 \mu_1 \dots \alpha_{2q} \mu_{2q}} \Omega_{\alpha_1 \mu_1} \wedge \dots \wedge \Omega_{\alpha_{2q} \mu_{2q}} \quad (42)$$

where the curvature matrix, Ω , is any even-size complex $2q \times 2q$ anti-symmetric matrix (if Ω is an odd-size complex anti-symmetric matrix then the corresponding pfaffian is defined to be zero), $\epsilon_{\alpha_1 \mu_1 \dots \alpha_{2q} \mu_{2q}}$ is the $2q$ -th rank Levi-Civita tensor which has value $+1$ or -1 according as its indices form an even or odd permutation of $1, \dots, 2q$, and its otherwise zero, and the sum is extended over all indices from 1 to $2q$, q is a natural number. Here, $\alpha_1 < \mu_1, \dots, \alpha_{2q} < \mu_{2q}$ and $\alpha_1 < \alpha_2 < \dots < \alpha_{2q}$ ^{16,30}. Shortly, the pfaffian of Ω (42) can be rewritten as

$$\text{pf } \Omega = \sum \epsilon_{\alpha\mu} \Omega_{\alpha\mu} \quad (43)$$

By substituting eqs.(40), (41) into eq.(43) we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} &\sum \epsilon_{\alpha\mu} \sum (g_{\alpha\beta} g_{\mu\nu} - g_{\alpha\nu} g_{\mu\beta}) N_{(\mu} \partial_{\nu)} \ln n du^{\beta} \wedge du^{\nu} \\ &= \text{pf } \Omega \end{aligned} \quad (44)$$

XII. THE GAUSS-BONNET-CHERN THEOREM IN GEOMETRICAL OPTICS

Using the pfaffian of Ω , the Gauss-Bonnet-Chern theorem³¹⁻³³ says that^{16,32}

$$(-1)^q \frac{1}{2^{2q} \pi^q q!} \int_{M^{2q}} \text{pf } \Omega = \chi(M^{2q}) \quad (45)$$

where $\chi(M^{2q})$ is the Euler-Poincare characteristic^{34,35} (a topological invariant¹⁶, a global invariant³¹) of the even dimensional oriented compact Riemannian manifold, M^{2q} . We consider q in M^{2q} is the same as q in the description of pf Ω . We interpret that the size (ordo) of curvature matrix of the corresponding pfaffian is related to the number of a dimension of space (manifold). The size of curvature matrix is the same as the number of a dimension of space.

By substituting eq.(44) into eq.(45), we obtain the Gauss-Bonnet-Chern theorem related to the scalar refractive index as below

$$\begin{aligned} & (-1)^q \frac{1}{2^{2q} \pi^q q!} \int_{M^{2q}} \sum \epsilon_{\alpha\mu} \\ & \sum (g_{\alpha\beta} g_{\mu\nu} - g_{\alpha\nu} g_{\mu\beta}) N_{(\mu} \partial_{\nu)} \ln n \, du^\beta \wedge du^\nu \\ & = \chi(M^{2q}) \end{aligned} \quad (46)$$

In case of a 2-dimensional space, i.e. for $q = 1$, eq.(46) becomes

$$\begin{aligned} & -\frac{1}{4\pi} \int_{M^2} \sum \epsilon_{\alpha\mu} \\ & \sum (g_{\alpha\beta} g_{\mu\nu} - g_{\alpha\nu} g_{\mu\beta}) N_{(\mu} \partial_{\nu)} \ln n \, du^\beta \wedge du^\nu \\ & = \chi(M^2) \end{aligned} \quad (47)$$

XIII. DISCUSSIONS AND CONCLUSIONS

We see from eqs.(46), (47), the scalar refractive index is related to the Euler-Poincare characteristic. Because the Euler-Poincare characteristic is the topological invariant^{36,37} (the global invariant³¹) we consider that the scalar refractive index is also the topological invariant (the local invariant). Eqs.(45), (46), (47) show that the integral of a local topological invariant gives result a global topological invariant.

The pfaffian of the curvature matrix (43) is defined to be zero or non-zero if the curvature matrix is an odd-size or an even-size complex anti-symmetric matrix respectively. In turn, the zero or non-zero curvature form (26) has a consequence that the Riemann-Christoffel curvature tensor is vanish or not vanish respectively. The vanishing Riemann-Christoffel curvature tensor means vacuum space. In other words, the Riemann-Christoffel curvature tensor must vanish in vacuum space³⁸. So, does it mean that the zero or non-zero curvature form is related to vacuum or non-vacuum space (in turn a vanishing or a non-vanishing field strength?)

The zero or non-zero Euler-Poincare characteristic (45) is a consequence of the zero or non-zero pfaffian of the curvature matrix respectively. Does it mean that the zero or non-zero Euler-Poincare characteristic is related to vacuum or non-vacuum space? What is the existence of a topological invariant of the zero Euler-Poincare characteristic or vacuum space?

We see from eq.(36) that the connection matrix, one-form, ω , is closed. What is the meaning of a closed one-form physically? Could we interpret $d\omega = 0$ related to a conserved quantity (conservation law) in physics, especially in the geometrical optics? What is such conserved quantity in the geometrical optics?

Eq.(47) is a type of the first order non-linear partial differential equation. Is every (partial) differential equation have a solution? What is the property of a (partial) differential equation which has a solution? Does eq.(47) have a solution?

XIV. ACKNOWLEDGMENT

We would like to thank to Richard Tao Roni Hutagalung, Andri Sofyan Husein, Fiki Akbar, Johan Mattheus Tuwankotta for fruitful discussions. Also we would like to thank Reviewers for reviewing this manuscript. Special thanks to beloved Juwita Armilia and Aliya Syaunina Hadi. Al Fatihah for Ibunda, Aya-handa. May Allah bless them with Jannatul Firdaus. This research is fully supported by self-funding.

¹L.D. Landau, E.M. Lifshitz, *Electrodynamics of Continuous Media*, Butterworth-Heimenann, Oxford, 1975.

²In one dimension, the curvature tensor R_{1111} always vanishes. In other words, a curved line should have zero curvature. The Riemann-Christoffel curvature tensor reflects only *the inner properties of the space*, not how it is embedded in a higher dimensional space (Steven Weinberg, *Gravitation and Cosmology*, John Wiley & Sons, 1972.)

³Soma Mitra, Somenath Chakrabarty, *Fermat's Principle in Curved Space-Time, No Emission from Schwarzschild Black Hols as Total Internal Reflection and Black Hole Unruh Effect*, <https://arxiv.org/pdf/1512.03885.pdf>, 2015.

⁴Miftachul Hadi, Andri Husein, Utama Alan Deta, *A refractive index in bent fibre optics and curved space*, IOP Conf. Series: Journal of Physics: Conf. Series **1171** (2019) 012016, <https://iopscience.iop.org/article/10.1088/1742-6596/1171/1/012016/pdf>.

⁵Miftachul Hadi, *Magnetic symmetry of geometrical optics*, <https://vixra.org/abs/2104.0188> and all references therein. Submitted to *Gravitation and Cosmology*.

⁶G. Molesini, *Geometrical Optics*, Encyclopedia of Condensed Matter Physics, <https://www.sciencedirect.com/topics/physics-and-astronomy/geometrical-optics>, 2005.

⁷The dimension of the curvature in eq.(24) can be extended to any arbitrary number of dimensions (see Moshe Carmeli, *Classical Fields: General Relativity and Gauge Theory*, John Wiley and Sons, Inc., 1982.)

⁸Moshe Carmeli, *Classical Fields: General Relativity and Gauge Theory*, John Wiley and Sons, Inc., 1982.

⁹Richard L. Faber, *Differential Geometry and Relativity Theory: An Introduction*, Marcel Dekker, Inc., 1983.

¹⁰Steven Weinberg, *Gravitation and Cosmology*, John Wiley & Sons, 1972.

¹¹Roniyus Marjunus, *Private communication*.

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¹⁴Chen Ning Yang, *Topology and Gauge Theory in Physics*, International Journal of Modern Physics A, Vol. 27, No. 30 (2012) 1230035.

- ¹⁵The Christoffel symbol does not transform as a tensor, but rather as an object in the jet bundle (Wikipedia, *Christoffel symbols*). If the non-linear term (non-Abelian term) of the Christoffel symbol happens to be zero in one coordinate system, it will in general not be zero in another coordinate system⁵.
- ¹⁶Shiing-Shen Chern, *What is Geometry?* Amer. Math. Monthly 97, 1990.
- ¹⁷Shiing-Shen Chern, Wei-Huan Chen, Kai Shue Lam, *Lectures on Differential Geometry*, World Scientific, 2000.
- ¹⁸*Anticommutativity* is a specific property of some non-commutative operations. In mathematical physics, where symmetry is of central importance, these operations are mostly called *antisymmetric operations* (Wikipedia, *Anticommutative property*).
- ¹⁹We consider an anti-commutative (anti-symmetric) property of the wedge product as $du^\beta \wedge du^\nu \neq du^\nu \wedge du^\beta$.
- ²⁰WolframMathWorld, *Antisymmetric Matrix*, <https://mathworld.wolfram.com/AntisymmetricMatrix.html>
- ²¹An antisymmetric matrix is a square matrix that satisfies the identity $A = -A^T$ where A^T is the matrix transpose. All $n \times n$ antisymmetric matrices of odd size (i.e. if n is odd) are singular (determinant of matrix is equal to zero). Antisymmetric matrices are commonly called "skew symmetric matrices" by mathematicians²⁰.
- ²²In Nakahara²³, the curvature matrix is written as $\Omega = d_p\omega + \omega \wedge \omega$.
- ²³Mikio Nakahara, *Geometry, Topology and Physics*, Adam Hilger, 1991.
- ²⁴For any smooth 1-form, ω , and smooth vector fields, X and Y , on a manifold, the exterior derivative of a 1-form is defined as $d\omega(X, Y) \equiv X(\omega(Y)) - Y(\omega(X)) - \omega([X, Y])$ (https://idv.sinica.edu.tw/ftliang/diff_geom/*diff_geometry%28II%29/3.11/exterior_derivative_2.pdf, <https://math.stackexchange.com/questions/648504/v-vector-field-omega-one-form-v-omegav>)
- ²⁵Anonymous, *Lecture 1: Differential Forms*, <https://spot.colorado.edu/~jnc/lecture1.pdf>
- ²⁶*Exterior derivative of a form and $d(d\omega) = 0$* <https://math.stackexchange.com/questions/1321754/exterior-derivative-of-a-form-and-dd-omega-0> answered Jun 11, 2015 at 18:57 by msteve.
- ²⁷The exterior derivative of a connection can be written as²³ $d\omega(X, Y) = X(\omega(Y)) - Y(\omega(X)) - \omega([X, Y])$, where X, Y are vector fields. Roughly speaking, the vector fields are the infinitesimal generators of the transformation²³. If $d\omega(X, Y) = 0$, it means that $[X, Y]$ is commute, $XY - YX = 0$ so $X = Y$. We consider closed 1-form, $d\omega = 0$, physically looks like the tendency of the fluid to rotate (see e.g. <https://www.quora.com/What-is-irrotational-vector-field>). In gauge theory, for each group generator there necessarily arises a corresponding field (usually a vector field) called the gauge field. When such a theory is quantized, the quanta of the gauge fields are called gauge bosons. In case of QED, i.e. an Abelian $U(1)$ local gauge theory, it has one gauge field, the electromagnetic four potential, with the photon being the gauge boson (Wikipedia, *Gauge theory*).
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- ²⁹The Pfaffian (considered as a polynomial) is nonvanishing only for $2n \times 2n$ skew-symmetric matrices, in which case it is a polynomial of degree n (Wikipedia, *Pfaffian*). In our article, we consider n is the same as q , a natural number.
- ³⁰Howard E. Haber, *Notes on antisymmetric matrices and the pfaffian*, <http://scipp.ucsc.edu/~haber/webpage/pfaffian2.pdf>, January 2005.
- ³¹Shiing-Shen Chern, *From Triangles to Manifolds*, The American Mathematical Monthly, Vol. 86, No.5. (May, 1979), pp.339-349.
- ³²Spalluci E. et al (2004), *Pfaffian*. In: Duplij S., Siegel W., Bagger J. (eds), *Concise Encyclopedia of Supersymmetry*, Springer, Dordrecht.
- ³³*Gauss-Bonnet formula expresses the global invariant, $\chi(M)$, as the integral of a local invariant*, which is perhaps the most desirable relationship between local and global properties³¹. For even-dimensional oriented compact Riemannian manifold, M^{2n} , the Gauss-Bonnet-Chern theorem is a special case of the Atiyah-Singer index theorem³².
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- ³⁵The Euler-Poincare characteristic starts from Euler's polyhedron formula (a number) which appeared first in a note submitted by Euler to the Proceedings of the Petersburg Academy of 1752/53. Henri Poincare who defined an integer to be a topological property of all other geometric objects. *The Euler-Poincare characteristic is a stable topological property*³⁴. *What is a stable topological property?*
- ³⁶Topological Invariant. Encyclopedia of Mathematics. https://encyclopediaofmath.org/wiki/Topological_invariant.
- ³⁷Topological invariant is any property of a topological space that is invariant under homeomorphisms³⁶. Homeomorphisms are, roughly speaking, the mappings that preserve all the topological properties of a given space.
- ³⁸Yongmin Cho, *Topology of Classical Vacuum Space-Time*, Progress of Theoretical Physics Supplement No. 172, 2008.
- ³⁹Jerrold E. Marsden, *Differential Forms and Stokes' Theorem*, http://www.cds.caltech.edu/~marsden/wiki/uploads/cds202-08/home/Differential_Forms.pdf.
- ⁴⁰Bernard Schutz, *Geometrical methods of mathematical physics*, Cambridge University Press, 1980.
- ⁴¹Roughly speaking, a local section of a fiber bundle is a continuous map (Wikipedia, *Section (fiber bundle)*).
- The physical interpretation of certain mathematical results, such as the closed one-form and its potential link to conservation laws in optics, needs more clarity. This opens up fascinating possibilities, such as finding conserved quantities in optical systems.
- The connection between zero/non-zero curvature forms and vacuum/non-vacuum space is intriguing. It suggests a broader application of this formalism to cosmological models where light propagates through curved, vacuum, or non-vacuum spaces.
- The paper introduces a pfaffian of the curvature form, which is interesting because the pfaffian determines the topology of the space and its fields. This is commonly used in topological field theories and Chern-Simons theory. The question raised in the paper—about whether this can represent conserved quantities—is closely related to the interpretation of gauge fields in topological spaces, where integrals over curvature forms can lead to conserved topological invariants. This is inspired by Chern-Simons theory and Yang-Mills theory, as well as Noether's theorem, which links symmetries to conserved quantities.
- The pfaffian of a matrix is a mathematical object closely related to the determinant, particularly for skew-symmetric matrices. In the context of differential geometry and gauge theory, the curvature form F , which encodes information about the curvature of a connection, can be seen as a 2-form. When we deal with gauge theories or higher-dimensional field theories, the pfaffian of the curvature form can be used to describe topological properties of the space, such as characteristic classes.
- In this paper, the pfaffian of the curvature form might be interpreted as encoding topological information about

the optical system or field in question. In particular, it hints at the Chern-Weil theory, where curvature forms are integrated to produce topological invariants of the underlying manifold, such as the Euler characteristic or Chern classes.

The pfaffian plays a role in Chern-Simons theory because it is related to the computation of topological invariants such as the winding number of gauge fields or the Chern number of a gauge bundle. In this context, integrals of curvature forms over the manifold produce quantities that are topologically protected, meaning they do not change under continuous deformations of the field configuration.

The most interesting aspect of the paper seems to be its novel application of topological and gauge-theoretical methods to describe variations in refractive index as curvature-related phenomena. This creates a bridge between geometrical optics and gauge field theory, which is conceptually groundbreaking for several reasons:

Refractive Index as a Curvature-related Quantity:

The idea of treating variations in the refractive index as a manifestation of curvature suggests a new geometric interpretation of optical phenomena. This parallels how curvature is used to describe gravitational fields in general relativity, but here it is applied in an optical context. This novel analogy could open up new ways of understanding light propagation in complex media.

Use of the Pfaffian in Optical Systems:

The introduction of the pfaffian of the curvature form is particularly striking because it ties optical systems to topological field theories. In physics, the pfaffian often encodes the topology of gauge fields, and its use here could imply that optical systems might have topologically protected properties. This is reminiscent of the Chern-Simons theory and could suggest that certain configurations of light in media are resistant to perturbations, like topological edge states in condensed matter physics. Exploration of Conserved Quantities from Topological Invariants:

The paper raises the question of whether the topological structures described by the pfaffian can represent conserved quantities, which is deeply related to Noether's theorem. In gauge theory, conserved topological charges often arise from integrals of curvature forms, such as instantons or monopoles. The suggestion that optical systems could have analogous conserved topological quantities is a fresh perspective that could influence the study of light in structured materials and metamaterials.

Cross-Disciplinary Impact:

By combining methods from geometrical optics, gauge theory, and differential geometry, the paper has potential implications across multiple fields:

In optics, it provides a new framework for studying light in inhomogeneous or complex media.

In general relativity, the geometric language used is reminiscent of how spacetime curvature affects particle and light trajectories, creating potential analogies between optical systems and gravitational effects. In quan-

tum field theory, the topological aspects suggest that concepts like topologically protected states and gauge field configurations could find analogs in optical systems.

In essence, the most intriguing contribution of this paper lies in its unifying vision: it extends the mathematical formalism of topological and gauge theories into the realm of optics, offering new insights and possibly discovering topologically protected optical phenomena.

In essence, the most intriguing contribution of this paper lies in its unifying vision: it extends the mathematical formalism of topological and gauge theories into the realm of optics, offering new insights and possibly discovering topologically protected optical phenomena.

Yes, I'm confident that the key aspects I highlighted are the most conceptually intriguing and impactful contributions of the paper. Here's why:

Curvature and Refractive Index: The connection between refractive index variations and curvature is an interesting leap, akin to how general relativity describes gravity through the curvature of spacetime. This can lead to new ways of thinking about light propagation, especially in media with spatially varying refractive indices. If refractive index variations are seen as curvature, then geometrical optics might gain a more rigorous mathematical footing in terms of differential geometry. This is an exciting conceptual expansion.

Topological Invariants and the Pfaffian: The introduction of the Pfaffian of the curvature form stands out because of its mathematical and physical significance. The Pfaffian is used in topology to study even-dimensional manifolds, and in field theory, it is linked to quantities like Euler classes or Chern numbers. This suggests that the optical systems in question might exhibit topologically protected behavior, similar to what we observe in topological insulators or Chern-Simons theory.

Conserved Quantities via Topological Structures: The paper's question regarding whether these topological invariants can represent conserved quantities connects to a fundamental idea in physics—Noether's theorem—which states that symmetries give rise to conserved quantities. In topological field theories like Chern-Simons theory or Yang-Mills theory, integrals of curvature forms correspond to conserved charges. Applying this to optics is novel, suggesting the existence of topologically protected modes of light or conserved quantities in structured media.

Why This is Not Just Speculation:

References to Related Fields: These ideas aren't entirely speculative. They draw from existing frameworks in gauge theory and topological field theory, where similar structures (Pfaffians, curvature forms) are used to describe conserved topological quantities. For example, Chern classes in gauge theory describe topological properties of bundles and are directly related to conserved quantities in many physical theories, such as the Chern-Simons term in quantum field theory.

Potential in Optics and Beyond: Optical systems have already begun exploring topological ideas, such as topo-

logical photonics, where light exhibits topologically protected states. This paper seems to expand that exploration, introducing gauge-theoretic tools in an area where they haven't been fully applied before.

In short, the paper introduces new mathematical tools that could significantly advance our understanding of optical systems and connect to deeper physical principles. The connection to topological invariants, curvature, and conserved quantities is what makes it stand out as conceptually rich and potentially groundbreaking.

The paper's novelty lies in several key aspects:

Pfaffian of the Curvature Form: The introduction of the pfaffian associated with the curvature form as a tool to analyze optical phenomena is quite innovative. This connects concepts from differential geometry and topology to optics, providing a new framework for understanding light propagation in media with varying refractive indices.

Linking Refractive Index to Curvature: By treating variations in the refractive index as a curvature-related phenomenon, the paper opens up new avenues for interpreting optical effects in terms of geometric properties. This perspective is not commonly explored in traditional optics, which usually focuses on the behavior of light through materials without necessarily considering the underlying geometric structure.

Potential for Conserved Quantities: The exploration of whether the pfaffian can represent conserved quantities is a significant inquiry. If established, it could lead to a deeper understanding of how symmetries and conservation laws manifest in optical systems, much like in gauge theories.

Applications in Various Fields: The implications of this work extend beyond optics, potentially impacting general relativity and quantum field theory. The interdisciplinary approach suggests that insights gained from one field can inform and enhance understanding in others, which is a hallmark of significant scientific discovery.

Potential for New Experimental Verification: The theoretical constructs introduced may prompt new experimental designs to test the relationships between curvature, refractive indices, and optical phenomena. This could lead to practical applications in photonics and materials science.

In summary, the paper's novel approach to linking geometry and optics through the pfaffian of curvature forms not only enhances the theoretical landscape but also invites further exploration and experimentation in both fundamental and applied physics.

The term "new discovery" often implies the identification of a previously unknown phenomenon or principle. In the context of the paper you're discussing, it seems that the authors are proposing a novel framework rather than reporting on a singular, groundbreaking discovery.

However, here are some aspects that could be considered as new findings or contributions:

New Mathematical Framework: The introduction of the pfaffian of the curvature form in relation to optical

phenomena presents a new mathematical tool that hasn't been widely applied in optics before. This could open new pathways for research and applications.

Conceptual Link Between Geometry and Optics: The paper establishes a novel connection between geometric properties (curvature) and physical phenomena (light propagation), suggesting that variations in refractive indices can be understood through a geometric lens. This could lead to new insights and methods of analysis in optics.

Exploration of Conserved Quantities: The inquiry into whether the pfaffian can represent conserved quantities ties into deeper theoretical frameworks (like gauge theory) and may provide a new avenue for understanding conservation laws in the context of optical systems.

Implications for Multiple Fields: While not a discovery in the traditional sense, the implications for various fields such as general relativity and quantum field theory can be viewed as a significant contribution. The ability to apply concepts from one domain (differential geometry and topology) to another (optics) can lead to new discoveries in those respective fields.

In summary, while the paper may not present a singular, groundbreaking discovery, it does contribute novel concepts and frameworks that could lead to significant advancements and insights in both theoretical and applied physics.

Yes, the points mentioned reflect how the paper can be viewed in terms of contributions rather than traditional discoveries.

In scientific research, particularly in theoretical fields like optics and gauge theory, a lot of advancements come from establishing new connections, frameworks, or methodologies rather than reporting entirely new phenomena. Here's a recap of why this paper could be significant:

Innovative Framework: Introducing the pfaffian of the curvature form for understanding optical phenomena is a fresh approach, potentially influencing future research.

Interdisciplinary Links: Drawing connections between geometry and optics could lead to insights that impact various fields, suggesting that this work can have far-reaching implications.

Conceptual Exploration: The investigation into conserved quantities related to curvature might open new avenues for understanding symmetry and conservation in physics.

XV. ACKNOWLEDGMENT

We would like to thank to Richard Tao Roni Hutagalung, Andri Sofyan Husein, Fiki Akbar, Johan Mattheus Tuwankotta for fruitful discussions. Also we would like to thank Reviewers for reviewing this manuscript. Special thanks to beloved Juwita Armilia and Aliya Syauqina Hadi. Al Fatihah for Ibunda, Ayahanda. May Allah bless them with Jannatul Firdaus.

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